

Article

In Situ Nitrate Monitoring for Improved Fertigation in On-Demand Coupled Aquaponic Systems

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Abstract: Fertigation practices in soilless crop cultivation often rely on predetermined recipes, which may lead to suboptimal nutrient concentrations due to inherent human error or environmental fluctuations. To address this challenge, the integration of in situ real-time nutrient analyzers becomes imperative for ensuring the delivery of high-quality supply solutions. This study assesses the effectiveness of a real-time nitrate (NO_3^-) analyzer in optimizing the mineral composition of the nutrient solution for fertigating a decoupled aquaponic cucumber crop. The analyzer was integrated into the programmable logic controller of the greenhouse's hydroponic system. The NO_3^- analyzer was activated during solution preparation, dynamically adjusting the NO_3^- concentration based on real-time measurements from either the aquaculture or drainage solution by adding the necessary water or/and nutrients in order to prepare a solution to meet the needs of the crop. Four treatments were evaluated: hydroponics (HP), coupled aquaponics (CAP), decoupled aquaponics (DCAP) with EC adjustment, and decoupled aquaponics with NO_3^- adjustment (DCAP_N). Results indicated that the DCAP_N treatment, with NO_3^- adjustment, yielded the highest crop productivity, outperforming DCAP, HP, and CAP treatments by 7.4%, 21.2%, and 56.1%, respectively. Additionally, DCAP_N demonstrated superior water use efficiency (WUE) and fertilizer use efficiency (FUE), exhibiting a 21.5% and 52.5% increase over the HP treatment, respectively. These findings align with the European Green Deal's objectives by enhancing nutrient management practices, which are crucial for minimizing nutrient loss and ensuring the sustainable and efficient use of fertilizers.

Keywords: aquaponics; real-time nitrate monitoring; fertigation management; water use efficiency; fertilizer use efficiency

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1. Introduction

Soilless agriculture, encompassing techniques such as hydroponics and aquaponics, offers substantial benefits in terms of water use efficiency and precise nutrient management. Aquaponics, the symbiotic cultivation of plants and fish, has only recently been studied in depth, while hydroponics has a more extensive research history. In modern aquaponics systems, water recirculates between the fish tanks and plant beds, forming a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) [1]. The fish-based water in the RAS has significantly higher concentrations of essential nutrients, such as nitrate (NO_3^-), compared to groundwater commonly used in hydroponics, making it an important nutrient source for soilless crops. However, since the drainage from the crops in coupled aquaponics systems is recirculated back to the fish tanks, it is challenging to optimize conditions for both fish and plant production simultaneously [2]. Plants require balanced amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium for optimal growth and yield. Nitrogen promotes vegetative growth and fruit setting, phosphorus supports root development and energy transfer, potassium enhances fruit quality and disease resistance, while calcium enhances photosynthesis and

fruit quality. Together, these nutrients are essential for healthy plant development and maximizing production [3]. Crop production is often compromised in coupled aquaponic systems due to the inability to supplement additional nutrients without adversely affecting fish health. This limitation results in significantly lower yields compared to other cultivation methods that optimize parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), and nutrient ratios through the use of chemical fertilizers. To mitigate these challenges, decoupled aquaponics systems have emerged as a solution to the low productivity issues inherent in coupled systems, allowing for independent management over aquaculture and hydroponic conditions, thereby providing a more effective solution for enhancing both plant growth and fish production [4]. In such systems, fish and plants are treated as independent units, with parameters related to the efficiency of each unit managed separately. This approach allows for optimal growth in both the aquaculture and hydroponic components, even though they are interconnected [5]. For plant growth, fertilizers can be added to the water derived from the aquaculture system to meet the specific nutrient requirements of the crops, ensuring enhanced productivity [6]. A key disadvantage of decoupled aquaponics systems is the suboptimal adjustment of nutrient concentrations. In a recent study, Aslanidou et al. [4] prepared the nutrient solution for fertigrating plants in a decoupled system based on weekly RAS water analyses, supplementing the remaining nutrients to reach the targeted concentrations for hydroponic crops. However, nutrient concentrations in decoupled aquaponic systems may not match the precise formulations typically recommended for hydroponic systems. Previous research often added fertilizers only up to 25% of the standard or without analyzing the RAS solution [7]. On the contrary, hydroponics usually adheres to specific nutrient profiles designed to optimize plant growth, whereas aquaponic systems derive their nutrients from fish waste, which may not perfectly align with these recommendations [2].

Traditionally, nutrient monitoring in aquaculture, aquaponic, and hydroponic systems is conducted in laboratories, necessitating manual sampling [8]. This approach is labor-intensive, time-consuming, and costly, as it requires sample collection followed by laboratory analyses, primarily through colorimetric techniques [8,9]. Additionally, this periodic monitoring can be problematic in systems involving living organisms, such as aquaculture systems, where delays in detecting nutrient imbalances can have catastrophic consequences.

Currently, there are numerous analytical methods for in situ detection of nitrate and nitrite, including UV spectroscopy, chromatography, electrochemistry, and various colorimetric methods. One of the most commonly employed methods for nutrient determination, specifically for NO_3^- ions, involves spectrophotometry following the Griess reaction [8,10,11]. According to Butinyac et al. [9], various direct ultraviolet nutrient analyzers are capable of performing real-time measurements. However, the accuracy of these detection probes is often significantly affected by other substances present in the sample, complicating their implementation in aquaculture systems. Ion chromatography (IC) is a widely used laboratory technique for analyzing inorganic anions, such as NO_3^- , in water resources. This method offers several significant advantages over colorimetric methods, including the use of fewer and non-hazardous chemicals, minimal to no sample preparation, and the ability to accurately target and measure specific ions even in complex samples with multiple interfering substances [12]. Murray et al. [13,14] introduced an innovative device that combines rapid ion chromatography with a 235 nm LED and a photodiode for direct UV detection, enabling highly selective and accurate analysis of these anions. Unlike traditional laboratory-based IC systems, this analyzer is designed to be portable and can be deployed in the field. This allows for on-site, real-time analysis of water samples, eliminating the need to transport samples to a laboratory.

This work aimed to assess a real-time, in situ NO_3^- nutrient analyzer for the monitoring and management of decoupled aquaponics systems. The analyzer dynamically adjusted the NO_3^- concentration based on real-time measurements by adding the necessary water or/and nutrients to prepare an irrigation solution tailored to the crop's needs. Specifically, the study aimed to (a) monitor and adjust the nitrate content of the irrigation solution based

on crop requirements, and (b) compare the impact of real-time, in situ NO_3^- monitoring on crop productivity, water use efficiency (WUE), and fertilizer use efficiency (FUE).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental Conditions and Plant Material

An experiment was conducted in the aquaponic greenhouse facilities of the Laboratory of Agricultural Constructions and Environmental Control, at the University of Thessaly, in the area of Velestino (latitude $39^\circ 44'$, longitude $22^\circ 79'$, altitude 85 m), Greece. The greenhouse encompassed a total ground area of 432 m^2 . Within this space, 80 m^2 was designated as a closed environment with controlled conditions, housing a RAS system for the rearing of red fish tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.). The remaining 352 m^2 of the greenhouse was allocated for the installation of experimental cultures, while portions of this area were dedicated to tanks containing concentrated nutrient solutions for the preparation of final supply solutions specific to each treatment. The climatic conditions within the cultivated area were automatically monitored using a climate control computer (Emmanouilidis, Thessaloniki, Greece). A schematic representation as well as a detailed description of the RAS system is presented in the recently published works by Aslanidou et al. [4] and Mourantian et al. [15]. The fish were stocked into three tanks with initial average fish weights of 272.9 ± 60.5 g, 476.9 ± 81.5 g, and 727.6 ± 134.7 g, respectively. The fish were hand-fed dry feed to satiation three times per day. The fish food (Prodac Pond Sticks Color, PRO.D.AC. INTERNATIONAL S.r.l., Padova, Italy) was composed of 29.0% crude protein, 5.7% crude ash, 3.3% crude fiber, 2.9% crude fat, 4.8% moisture, 42.2% omega-6, and 5.7% omega-3 fatty acids. The total biomass across all three tanks started at 136.4 kg on the first experimental day.

A total of 276 cucumber plants (*Cucumis sativa* cv. Colombia) were transplanted into 138 perlite bags (Hydroperl 33 L, Nordiaagro, Athens, Greece) at a planting density of 1.18 plants m^{-2} . The transplantation occurred when the plants had reached the fifth true leaf stage. The experiment lasted from September to December 2023, with a total time of 86 days. The greenhouse was divided into three adjacent compartments, each containing six hydroponic channels (experimental units). All treatments were cultivated under similar climatic conditions, as the plants were transplanted in the same greenhouse. The following four fertigation treatments were applied to the soilless cucumber crop, with hydroponics serving as the control treatment:

- hydroponics (HP), using a standard supply solution (SS) for cucumber crops (one experimental unit/compartiment, i.e., three replications)
- coupled aquaponics (CAP), using RAS water after pH adjustment (one experimental unit/compartiment, i.e., three replications)
- decoupled aquaponics (DCAP), using RAS water enriched with nutrients after pH and EC adjustment (two experimental units/compartiment, i.e., six replications), and
- decoupled aquaponics with NO_3^- adjustment (DCAP_N), using RAS water enriched with nutrients after NO_3^- adjustment (two experimental units/compartiment, i.e., six replications)

Consequently, the HP and CAP treatments each occupied three experimental units, corresponding to 46 plants per treatment, whilst the DCAP and DCAP_N treatments each occupied six experimental units, corresponding to 92 plants per treatment. Plants of the HP treatment were fertigated with a standard SS formulated for soilless cucumber crops cultivated in arid- and semi-arid regions containing 13.6 mM N- NO_3^- , 1.4 mM N- NH_4^+ , 1.15 mM H_2PO_4 , 7.2 mM K^+ , 3.4 mM Ca^{2+} , 1.4 mM Mg^{2+} , 1.4 mM S- SO_4 , 15.0 μM Fe, 25.0 μM B, 0.8 μM Cu, 5.0 μM Zn, 10.0 μM Mn, 0.5 μM Mo. For the DCAP treatment, fish water was collected from the RAS weekly, and based on its nutrient analysis, fertilizers were added to achieve the same mineral composition as in the HP treatment. Conversely, the supply solution for the DCAP_N treatment was prepared similarly to the DCAP treatment but with a specific focus on adjusting the nitrate concentration. Plants of all treatments were drip fertigated using irrigation drippers with a flow rate of 2 Lh^{-1} . A custom controller

(Argos Electronics, Evia, Greece) continuously and automatically regulated the fertigation of all treatments.

2.2. Nitrate Management of the Supply Solution

A portable nitrate (NO_3^-) and nitrite (NO_2^-) analyzer (NO_x -monitrix Mobile, Aquamonitrix Ltd., Tullow, Carlow, Ireland) was deployed within the closed environment, housing the RAS system. The analyzer combines rapid ion chromatography with low-power requirements of UV-LED detection delivering laboratory accuracy measurements of NO_3^- and NO_2^- in aquatic environments. The analyzer demonstrates an accuracy of 99% in freshwater and 95% in both wastewater and saline water, with precision reaching up to 95%. The integration of the in situ real-time nutrient analyzer aimed to ensure the delivery of high-quality nutrient solutions representing an innovative product for Integrated Nutrient Management. The analyzer was integrated into the existing programmable logic controller (PLC) of the greenhouse's hydroponic system to monitor and control the NO_3^- concentration of the DCAP_N treatment. Traditionally, nutrient solutions are prepared based on EC values, with specific targets such as 2.3 dS m^{-1} for cucumber crops. Prior to integrating the analyzer, the hydroponic system would adjust water, stock nutrient solutions and acid to meet predetermined EC and pH levels, following standard hydroponic practices. However, in this experiment, the $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ analyzer was introduced to modify the system setup. Instead of relying solely on EC values, the system was adapted to prepare nutrient solutions for crop fertigation aiming to achieve the "target" nitrate concentration, potentially resulting in varying EC levels.

In this study, 30% of the drainage solution (DS) of each treatment was collected and reused as a supply solution for the corresponding treatment. To prepare 100 L of SS for the DCAP_N treatment, 30 L of DS were introduced into the hydroponic head tank. The analyzer was then activated to measure the NO_3^- content of the DS. Subsequently, 70 L of fish water were added into the tank. After another activation of the analyzer to re-measure the NO_3^- content, fertilizers were added based on the required nitrate concentration for cucumber crops. The analyzer was activated once more to measure the final NO_3^- content, which determined the SS used for fertigating the crop. The same process was followed for the HP, DCAP and AQ treatments. However, for these treatments, the analyzer was used solely for monitoring the NO_3^- concentration and not for controlling it.

2.3. Measurements

Measurements of plant height and number of leaves were conducted on a weekly basis. The plant height was measured using a calibrated ruler (accuracy of $\pm 0.5 \text{ cm}$), by determining the distance from the ground level to the upper boundary of the plant. To ensure accurate leaf count, the number of the leaves removed from the plants due to pruning practices was also considered. A total of 12 plants were randomly selected as sampling plants for each treatment ($n = 12$ plants per treatment). In addition, fruit harvesting was performed with a frequency of approximately 2–3 days per week and involved recording of the weight and number of fruits per sampling plant as well as the total productivity per treatment. Fruit weight measurements were performed using a precision scale (Precisa, Dietikon, Switzerland).

In total, three destructive measurements were conducted throughout the experimental period. In particular, these measurements were performed the following days after transplantation (DAT): DAT 25, DAT 51, and DAT 81. In each destructive measurement, four plants per treatment were randomly collected. The aboveground part of the plants was separated into leaves, stems, and fruits. After measuring the fresh weight per plant material, the different parts of the plant were placed in a drying oven at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 72 h until constant weight, to record the dry weight. Leaf tissue analysis was conducted for every destructive measurement. Subsequently, N, K, Ca^{2+} , and Na analysis was performed in the leaf tissue. The determination of non-volatile mineral composition in the plant tissue was carried out by high-temperature dry ashing of the organic matter, and 6% hydrochloric acid

solution. The leaf content in Ca, Na, and K was estimated using a flame photometer (PFP7, Jenway Technology Company, Hong Kong, China). The estimation of the total nitrogen in the leaf tissue was carried out via the Kjeldhal method [16].

The mineral composition of both the SS and DS was monitored weekly. Samples (four replications per treatment) were manually collected from the inlet and outlet of the system and their mineral composition was analyzed either on-site or in the laboratory. Specifically, the NO_3^- content was determined on-site using an updated version of the analyzer previously utilized for preparing the SS of the DCAP_N treatment. The second version of the $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ analyzer (NO_x -monitrix, Aquamonitrix Ltd., Tullow, Carlow, Ireland) was employed to measure the NO_3^- concentration in real time. The collected samples were analyzed for the determination of K, Na, Ca^{2+} using a flame photometer (PFP7 Flame Photometer, Jenway, Cole-Parmer Ltd., St. Neots, UK), while NH_4^+ , and PO_4^{3-} measurements were performed using a spectrophotometer (Hach, Loveland, CO, USA). Measurements of pH and EC were performed using a portable device (Hanna Instruments Inc., Woonsocket, RI, USA).

2.4. Calculations

The WUE was determined by calculating the ratio of the total cucumber yield (kg m^{-2}) to the total volume of the supplied nutrient solution ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-2}$) over the entire cultivation period. Similarly, the FUE was calculated by dividing the total yield (kg m^{-2}) by the total amount of fertilizer applied (kg m^{-2}) for each treatment. These calculations allowed for a direct comparison of resource efficiency between different nutrient management strategies.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Comparison of means was performed by applying one-way ANOVA at a confidence level of 95% ($p \leq 0.05$) using IBM SPSS Statistics 26 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Additionally, multiple comparison of means was performed using the LSD test at the 5% level of significance. In the case where the data did not follow a normal distribution, a non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test ($p \leq 0.05$) was applied. The mean values and standard errors ($\pm SE$) of the measured parameters are also reported.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Mineral Composition of the Irrigation and Drainage Solution

In an aquaponic system, nitrogen, mostly as nitrate, is the key nutrient that gets recycled from the fish to nourish plants. However, other essential elements such as potassium are usually in short supply in the fish water and often require additional supplementation with fertilizers [17]. As shown in Table 1, the integration of the NO_3^- analyzer into the fertigation management resulted in generally higher EC irrigation levels in the DCAP_N treatment, which subsequently led to higher NO_3^- and K content in the nutrient solution compared to the other measurements. In particular, the NO_3^- concentration in the DCAP_N treatment was similar to that of the HP; however, it was significantly higher by 4.2% and 49.8% than that in the DCAP and CAP treatments. Similarly, K content increased in the irrigation solution by 27.1%, 15.7%, and 81.7% compared to the HP, the DCAP, and the CAP treatments, respectively. Both elements are considered significant in both the vegetative (NO_3^-) and fruit (K) stages of cucumbers. Therefore, the integration of the analyzer in managing the DCAP_N solution resulted in increased NO_3^- and K concentration in the irrigation solution compared to a conventional DCAP treatment. Notwithstanding, the mineral composition of the drainage solution presented similar trends between the DCAP and DCAP_N, despite the different management of the irrigation solutions. The mineral nutrient composition of both the supply and drainage solutions in the CAP treatment was the lowest compared to all other treatments, as this system utilized water derived from the aquaculture system without the addition of extra nutrients.

Table 1. Mineral nutrient composition of the irrigation and drainage solution of the different fertigation treatments.

		pH	¹ EC	¹ NO ₃ ⁻	¹ NH ₄ ⁺	¹ PO ₄ ³⁻	¹ K	¹ Na	¹ Ca ²⁺
Irrigation	HP	6.32 ± 0.06 ^a	1.92 ± 0.03 ^a	9.08 ± 0.33 ^{ab}	0.35 ± 0.04 ^b	0.92 ± 0.08 ^a	4.49 ± 0.97 ^b	1.27 ± 0.26 ^{ab}	3.76 ± 0.69 ^a
	CAP	6.48 ± 0.07 ^a	1.11 ± 0.03 ^b	4.64 ± 0.11 ^c	0.03 ± 0.01 ^c	0.28 ± 0.01 ^b	1.13 ± 0.27 ^c	1.18 ± 0.27 ^b	1.76 ± 0.30 ^b
	DCAP	6.31 ± 0.06 ^a	2.05 ± 0.04 ^a	8.85 ± 0.27 ^b	0.70 ± 0.06 ^a	1.01 ± 0.13 ^a	5.19 ± 0.68 ^{ab}	1.35 ± 0.27 ^a	3.59 ± 0.63 ^a
	DCAP_N	6.32 ± 0.07 ^a	2.17 ± 0.05 ^a	9.24 ± 0.29 ^a	0.49 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	0.85 ± 0.08 ^a	6.16 ± 1.66 ^a	1.37 ± 0.25 ^a	3.22 ± 0.44 ^a
Drainage	HP	7.34 ± 0.12 ^{ab}	1.75 ± 0.09 ^a	7.25 ± 0.54 ^a	0.06 ± 0.02 ^a	0.42 ± 0.07 ^a	3.26 ± 1.84 ^a	2.32 ± 0.65 ^a	3.90 ± 0.65 ^a
	CAP	7.35 ± 0.07 ^a	0.79 ± 0.03 ^b	2.02 ± 0.14 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.23 ± 0.06 ^b	0.98 ± 0.71 ^b	1.71 ± 0.48 ^b	1.82 ± 0.45 ^b
	DCAP	7.01 ± 0.09 ^b	2.01 ± 0.07 ^a	7.74 ± 0.49 ^a	0.13 ± 0.04 ^a	0.35 ± 0.06 ^a	3.57 ± 2.21 ^a	2.41 ± 0.62 ^a	4.26 ± 0.81 ^a
	DCAP_N	7.02 ± 0.08 ^b	2.15 ± 0.11 ^a	7.40 ± 0.52 ^a	0.12 ± 0.02 ^a	0.54 ± 0.08 ^a	5.80 ± 2.88 ^a	2.51 ± 0.58 ^a	3.93 ± 0.90 ^a

¹ EC in dS m⁻¹; concentration of all macronutrients (NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, PO₄³⁻, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺) in mmol L⁻¹. Lowercase letters within a column indicate differences between treatments of either the irrigation or the drainage solution ($p < 0.05$).

In a recent study [18], the efficiency of an on-demand coupled aquaponic treatment for a basil crop was tested. Unlike the current study, Rodgers et al. [18] added only 25% of the mineral composition of a conventional hydroponic system to conserve nutrients. This strategy resulted in the decoupled aquaponic system having significantly lower concentrations of N, P, and Ca by 26%, 70%, and 54%, respectively, compared to standard hydroponics, leading to an 11% decrease in yield. In contrast, the present study used an in situ analyzer to maintain similar mineral compositions in both the HP and DCAP_N treatments, ensuring efficient yield performance.

3.2. Crop Nutrient Uptake

The mean mineral nutrient concentrations from each leaf tissue analyses conducted on DAT 25, DAT 51, and DAT 81 for each of the tested treatments are presented in Table 2. Despite varying fertigation management practices, no significant differences in nitrogen uptake by the leaves were observed between the treatments. Although the CAP treatment exhibited a lower nitrogen concentration, it was not statistically different from the other three treatments. In contrast, the CAP treatment recorded the lowest potassium and sodium accumulation in the leaf tissue compared to the HP, DCAP, and DCAP_N treatments. Regarding calcium uptake, plants under the DCAP_N treatment showed a 22.4% and 22.8% reduction in Ca²⁺ concentration compared to the HP and CAP treatments, respectively. However, no statistically significant results were obtained when compared to the DCAP treatment.

Table 2. Mineral nutrient content (mg g⁻¹) in cucumber leaves of the different fertigation treatments.

	N (mg g ⁻¹)	K (mg g ⁻¹)	Ca ²⁺ (mg g ⁻¹)	Na (mg g ⁻¹)
HP	41.57 ± 2.53 ^a	20.92 ± 2.79 ^a	55.76 ± 2.45 ^a	1.42 ± 0.13 ^{ab}
CAP	36.13 ± 1.33 ^a	9.44 ± 0.91 ^b	56.04 ± 2.74 ^a	0.94 ± 0.13 ^b
DCAP	41.03 ± 2.53 ^a	25.35 ± 0.04 ^a	47.96 ± 2.13 ^{ab}	1.62 ± 0.12 ^a
DCAP_N	40.49 ± 3.07 ^a	21.58 ± 2.77 ^a	45.31 ± 1.59 ^b	1.78 ± 0.23 ^a

Lowercase letters within a column indicate differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$).

In the present study, the integration of a nutrient analyzer into the nutrient management of a cucumber crop resulted in increased nitrate and potassium availability to the plants (Table 1). The results obtained from crop nutrient uptake analysis align with those of Rodgers et al. [18], who found no statistically significant differences in nitrogen and potassium uptake when comparing a conventional soilless basil crop to a decoupled aquaponic system treated with 25% supplementary fertilizers. Similarly, Aslanidou et al. [4] observed no differences in nutrient uptake for a soilless cucumber crop when comparing a crop fertigated with a standard supply solution (hydroponics) to one fertigated with fish water enriched with nutrients (DCAP).

3.3. Morphological Characteristics

The evolution of plant height for all the tested treatments during the cultivation period is presented in Figure 1a. As expected, plant height showed a gradual upward trend for all fertigation treatments. Significant differences were observed in the height of the coupled aquaponic plants (CAPs) which consistently had a statistically lower height compared to all other treatments from the start of the experiment. During the final measurement, the mean height recorded for the plants of the HP, DCAP, and DCAP_N treatments did not present any statistically significant difference. However, all the aforementioned treatments differ significantly from the mean height recorded for the CAP treatment by approximately 28.7%. Similar findings were reported by Aslanidou et al. [19], where conventional and on-demand coupled aquaponic cucumber plants had a roughly 40% greater height than those in the coupled aquaponic system. The HP, DCAP, and DCAP_N treatments followed a similar trend throughout the experimental series. These findings are consistent with those reported in the literature [1,5,20].

Figure 1. (a) Mean plant height (cm) and (b) mean number of leaves of the different treatments of the crop during the whole cultivation period. Lowercase letters indicate differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$) for each DAT.

The average number of leaves of the different treatments followed a generally similar trend to that of the plant height (Figure 1b). Specifically, the total number of leaves of the HP, DCAP, and DCAP_N treatment was on average 40.0 ± 1.2 , which is higher by 30% compared to the total number of leaves of the CAP treatment. Similarly, Aslanidou et al. [19] demonstrated a significant variation in leaf count between cucumber plants when comparing HP, DCAP, and CAP treatments, with the CAP treatment resulting in a notably lower number of leaves. The application of the NO_3^- analyzer for the fertigation management of the DCAP_N treatment did not significantly affect the plant height and the total number of leaves throughout the cultivation period, as no significant differences were recorded compared to either the HP or the DCAP treatment.

3.4. Yield, Water and Fertilizer Use Efficiency

An assessment was conducted on fertilizer use efficiency (FUE) and water use efficiency (WUE), as well as on yield performance and it is depicted in Table 3, revealing variations in cucumber productivity across different treatments. Monsees et al. [5] reported a 36% increase in tomato fruit yield when on-demand coupled aquaponics (decoupled aquaponics) was used, thanks to improved pH and fertilizer management compared to traditional aquaponics. Aslanidou et al. [19] demonstrated a 37% increase in cucumber yield in conventional and decoupled aquaponic systems compared to a coupled aquaponic system. Notably, in the present work, the DCAP_N treatment demonstrated the highest yield and total number of fruits, highlighting the importance of integrating the NO_3^- analyzer into the fertigation management. Compared to DCAP, HP, and CAP treatments, DCAP_N exhibited yield increases of 7.4%, 21.2%, and 56.1%, respectively. Similarly, the DCAP_N

treatment boasted the highest WUE value. In contrast to the findings of the present study, Suhl et al. [21] reported higher water use efficiency values in the HP treatment compared to DCAP. Numerous studies [22–24] have highlighted the nutritional benefits of fish-derived water, suggesting that the dissolved organic molecules, plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria, and/or plant growth-promoting fungi in the RAS solution may play a key role in enhancing plant growth. Therefore, the combination of fish water with advanced nutrient analyzers, such as the ion chromatography analyzer used in this study, may play a dual role in promoting plant growth. Contrary to the findings of the present work, a recent study by Rodgers et al. [18] failed to achieve optimal nutrient concentrations in a decoupled aquaponic system despite adding supplementary nutrients to the nutrient solution for a basil crop. In their study, Rodgers et al. [18] incorporated 25% of the chemical-based fertilizers typically used in hydroponics to reduce overall nutrient usage. However, this approach did not succeed in surpassing the performance of a conventional hydroponic system. This highlights the importance of implementing nutrient analyzers in such systems to address nutrient deficiencies and fulfill the crop's nutritional needs.

Table 3. Total fruit yield (kg m^{-2}), number of fruits (fruits m^{-2}), FUE (kg kg^{-1}), and WUE (kg m^{-3}) of the HP, DCAP, DCAP_N, and CAP treatments.

	HP	DCAP	DCAP_N	CAP
Productivity (kg m^{-2})	3.72 ^b	4.37 ^a	4.72 ^a	2.07 ^c
Number of fruits (fruit m^{-2})	15.3 ^b	18.4 ^a	19.5 ^a	9.0 ^c
FUE (kg kg^{-1} of fertilizers)	20.8 ^b	48.0 ^a	43.8 ^a	-
WUE (kg m^{-3} of supplied water)	60.7 ^b	74.3 ^a	77.3 ^a	-

Lowercase letters within a line indicate differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$).

The findings of this study align with those of Aslanidou et al. [4,19] and Calone et al. [24], who also observed a significantly lower yield performance in cucumber crops treated with pure aquaponic water. This reduction in yield is attributed to the mineral composition of the biologically derived fish water, which has considerably lower nutrient concentrations compared to hydroponic systems or on-demand coupled aquaponic practices that incorporate fertilizers [24,25].

However, in terms of FUE, the DCAP and DCAP_N treatments outperformed the HP treatments, as confirmed by several studies [4,5]. Monsees et al. [2] also reported that the on-demand coupled aquaponics system (DCAP) achieved comparable yields to hydroponics while using 62.8% fewer mineral nutrients and completely eliminating freshwater usage. Consistent with these findings, our study revealed that although DCAP_N had an 8.8% lower FUE than DCAP, it still showed a 52.5% increase in FUE compared to the HP treatment. This highlights the efficiency of nutrient recycling in aquaponics systems, where, unlike in hydroponics, the added fertilizers do not lead to significant differences in plant nutrient uptake or productivity. Notably, while the FUE of DCAP was higher than that of DCAP_N, the latter produced a higher yield due to the use of a nitrate analyzer. This result likely stems from the analyzer's role in optimizing nitrate concentration, which, when activated, not only adjusted NO_3^- levels but also added other nutrients into the system, leading to greater nutrient consumption in the DCAP_N treatment, albeit without a significant difference compared to DCAP. This suggests that the real-time nutrient monitoring provided by the nitrate analyzer offers a distinct advantage in yield optimization. In the preparation of stock solutions for DCAP treatments, fish water analysis serves as a reference point, with fertilizers added to attain the target EC equivalent to that of the HP treatment. However, while EC provides a general indication of total nutrient availability, it does not offer detailed information on the specific nutrients present, their concentrations, or their chemical forms [26]. As a result, this approach often falls short of achieving optimal nutrient levels in the final solution. The utilization of the $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ tool, however, notably enhances yield, WUE, and FUE compared to standard hydroponic methods, thus facilitating superior water and fertilizer management and yielding higher crop outputs.

Finally, in Table 3, it should be noted that the FUE and WUE values for the CAP treatment are absent. This is because no additional fertilizers or water inputs were utilized during the growth of the CAP plants.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results of this work, incorporating a nitrate analyzer in the nutrient management of a decoupled hydroponic system (DCAP_N) significantly improved the availability of nitrate and potassium in the irrigation solution, which are vital for cucumber growth. Despite these improvements, there were no significant differences in plant uptake of nutrients (nitrogen and potassium) compared to other systems, such as conventional hydroponics and decoupled aquaponics systems. However, the DCAP_N system resulted in higher cucumber yields and water and fertilizer use efficiency, demonstrating the benefits of using a nitrate analyzer to optimize nutrient management. The DCAP_N system showed the highest yield and WUE, outperforming hydroponic treatments. This highlights the importance of accurate nutrient management to improve the performance of aquaponic systems.

Real-time, in situ nutrient analyzers may revolutionize the monitoring and management of decoupled aquaponics systems. While this study provides valuable insights, there are several opportunities for future research to build on these findings. Further research could also focus on refining real-time nutrient monitoring technologies. Integrating additional analyzers, such as those for phosphorus or micronutrients, could help optimize a wider range of essential nutrients. Exploring how these technologies perform in larger-scale commercial systems, with different aquaculture species and varying water quality conditions, would offer valuable insights for scaling up aquaponics operations. To our knowledge, this is the first trial of a real-time in situ nitrate analyzer incorporation for nutrient management in on-demand coupled aquaponics or decoupled aquaponics.

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